

EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION OF A SEAL FLUTTER MODEL

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ABSTRACT

The predictions of an analytical model for seal flutter have been compared with the experimental data of a rotating multi-cavity labyrinth seal test rig. The experiments were conducted to assess the flutter inception in a large set of operating conditions by varying the rotational speed and the total pressure ratio across the seal. The sensitivity of the stability to the clearance variation is also studied for straight-through and stepped configurations. The analytical model derived by Corral et al. (2022, “Effective Clearance and Differential Gapping Impact on Seal Flutter Modelling and Validation,” ASME J. Turbomach, 144 (7), pp. 071010) has been previously validated by using a frequency domain linearized Navier-Stokes solver retaining the effect of the effective gaps and the kinetic energy carried over to downstream fin. To reduce the uncertainty, a set of 3D steady RANS simulations is performed and the steady characteristics of the seal are used to inform the flutter model. The effect of dissimilar gaps has been studied by generating a set of numerical models with geometrical gap differences. The stability limit has been investigated in a large range of operating conditions. Firstly, the non-dimensional parameters controlling seal flutter will be introduced, then the test rig, the test matrix, and the numerical setup of the simulations, are described. Finally, the experimental data are compared with the prediction of the analytical model in a wide range of operating conditions.

NOMENCLATURE

$a_j(t)$	j – th gap time perturbation
a_0	Sound speed in the cavity
A	Seal clearance area
C_d	$= \dot{m}/\dot{m}_{id}$, Discharge Coefficient
CV	Corral and Vega
h	Upstream fin non-dimensional pressure function
H	Fin clearance
HPS	High Pressure Side
L	Seal cavity length
LPS	Low Pressure Side
\dot{m}	Mass flow per span-wise or circumferential length unit
ND	Nodal diameter
p_c	Cavity static pressure
p_e	Exit static pressure
P_0	Inlet total pressure
r	Torsion center position
R	Cavity radius
Re	$= \dot{m}/(2\pi R\mu)$ Reynolds number based on the gap
R_g	Specific gas constant
s	Cavity height
\bar{s}	$= s/(\gamma H h')$, Nondimensional cavity height
J	Downstream fin non-dimensional pressure function
St	$= \frac{\omega R}{ND a_0}$, Vibration-to-acoustic frequency ratio
t	Tip fin thickness
t_d	$= \frac{p_{c,s} V_{c,s}}{\dot{m}_s a_0^2}$, Seal discharge time
TC	Torsion center

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v_θ	Circumferential velocity
W_{cyc}	Work per cycle
z	Azimuthal coordinate

Greek symbols

β	Jet opening angle
χ	kinetic energy carry-over coefficient
γ	Heat capacity ratio
η	$= H_2/H_1$. Gap ratio.
π_s	$= P_0/p_c$. Cavity pressure ratio
π_T	$= P_0/p_e$. Total pressure ratio
π_c	$= \pi_T/\pi_s$. Cavity exit pressure ratio.
ω	Vibration angular frequency (rad/s)
Ω	$= \omega t_d$ Non-dimensional discharge time
$\tilde{\Omega}$	$= \tilde{\Omega}/h'$. Ω rescaling with π_T
ρ	Fluid density
$\Delta\theta$	Rotation angle
τ	Non-dimensional time

Super-scripts

\sim	Non-dimensional values
$'$	Time perturbation

Sub-scripts

e	Exit
f	Fluid dynamic
g	Geometric
0	Total property
c	Cavity
cyc	cycle
s	Steady state
eff	Effective value

INTRODUCTION

Labyrinth seals are extensively used in turbomachinery to control the leakage flow between rotating and stationary components. They are commonly used in the secondary air system to supply cooling air and to prevent the ingestion of hot gas from the mainstream to the disk cavities. They are also used to minimize the leakage flow between the blade tip and the casing. Labyrinth seals are composed of a series of cavities connected by constrictions through which the flow is forced to pass. The acceleration through the clearances generates kinetic energy, which is then dissipated in the following cavity. This process produces losses reducing the leakage flow. For many years most of the studies regarding labyrinth seals have been efficiency-driven and focused on the seal steady flow characteristics.

Recently, Corral and Vega [1] released a new comprehensive physical-based seal flutter model reconciling the classical stability criteria of Ehrich [2] and Abbot [3]. Lately, Corral et al. [4] provided a new formulation of the model retaining the effect of non-isentropic perturbations and, more recently, the kinetic energy carried over to the downstream fin [5]. The model has been validated by a large set of 3D unsteady simulations considering

simplified two fin seals [5, 6].

A relevant parametric investigation on a multi-cavity seal was conducted by Phibel et al. [7] and Di Mare et al. [8], which studied an LP turbine labyrinth seal in two different configurations by using a time-marching Navier-Stokes solver. They highlighted that the classical stability criteria were not appropriate to describe the stability of a complex seal configuration. Lately, Miura and Sakai [9] released experimental data for a four-fin straight labyrinth seal. They compared the test data with CFD simulations showed a reasonably good agreement.

In this work, the critical reduced frequency of a rotating multi-cavity seal has been investigated in a large range of operating conditions. Firstly, the nondimensional parameters controlling seal flutter will be introduced, then the test rig, the test matrix and the numerical setup of the simulations are described. Finally, the experimental data are compared with the prediction of the analytical model in a wide range of operating conditions in to determine the validity of the stability criterion embedded in the model.

ANALYTICAL MODEL FOR SEAL FLUTTER

The baseline CV model [1] solves the linearised integral form of the mass-conservation equation of the inter-fin cavity and the differential form of the momentum equation in the circumferential direction, assuming an ideal flow. The isentropic condition is replaced by the integral form of the energy equation of the inter-fin cavity in the higher-order version of the model [10]. The circumferential variations of the unsteady perturbations are retained in the model whereas the spatial variations in the meridional plane of the cavity are neglected. The process is assumed adiabatic, and the work associated with the viscous forces is neglected. The seal vibration is imposed as a rigid body motion around a fixed torsion center, as shown in Fig. 1, and the spatio-temporal variations of the gaps, H , and the volume of the seal, have the form of travelling waves. Similarly, the linearised equations are solved by seeking solutions in the form of travelling waves also. The model takes into account the effects on the stability of the differential gapping and of the jet's kinetic energy carried over to the downstream fin of each cavity as described in [5].

The model accounts only for the work performed by the seal land since when the unsteady pressure is considered uniform within the inter-fin cavity the contribution of the fins cancels out, unless the seal is slanted. The reader is referred to [10] for further details of the formulation.

The dimensionless work-per-cycle can be written in closed form evaluating three nondimensional parameters only:

$$\tilde{W}_{cyc} = \tilde{W}_{cyc}(\tilde{\Omega}, St'(M_\theta, \beta), \tilde{e}h'_{eff},) \quad (1)$$

Even if the expression used to evaluate the stability is very compact and easy to use, some considerations on the nondimen-

FIGURE 1. Sketch of the labyrinth seal geometry

sional parameters involved are needed.

The nondimensional discharge time of the seal, representing the time needed to discharge the interfin cavity by closing the upstream clearance, is expressed as $\bar{\Omega} = \hat{\Omega}\Omega$ where:

$$\hat{\Omega} = \gamma \frac{1 + \gamma\Omega^2}{1 + \gamma^2\Omega^2}, \quad \Omega = \omega \frac{p_{c,s} V_{c,s}}{\dot{m}_s a_0^2}, \text{ and } \tilde{\Omega} = \frac{\Omega}{h'} \quad (2)$$

The nondimensional discharge time of the seal involves the mean static pressure in the inter-fin seal cavity, $p_{c,s}$, the volume of the seal, $V_{c,s}$, the mass flow, \dot{m}_s , the speed of sound, a_0 , and h' which is a involved function of the seal pressure ratio (see Fig. 1 for a summary of the nomenclature). The expression for h' involves the kinetic energy coefficient, χ , and the pressure ratios:

$$h' = h(\pi_s) + J(\pi_T/\pi_s) \frac{(1 - \chi)}{\pi_s \chi + (1 - \chi)} \quad (3)$$

where $\pi_s = P_0/p_c$ and $\pi_T = P_0/p_e$. The terms h and J are complex functions of the pressure ratio that can be found in the appendix of [1] and [5]. The combined expression retaining simultaneously the kinetic energy carried-over downstream and the non-isentropic perturbations is too complex to be written here and does not add much to the discussion.

The mechanical to acoustic frequency ratio based on the vibration frequency in the relative frame of reference of the fluid:

$$St' = St + M_\theta (\beta - 1) \quad (4)$$

where β is the so-called swirl factor, which relates the rotational velocity of the fluid and the disk ($\Omega_f = \beta \Omega_{Rotor}$). The swirl factor ranges between zero and one, and typically is $\beta \simeq 0.3$, while

$$St = \frac{\omega R}{ND a_0}, \text{ and } M_\theta = \frac{\Omega_{Rotor} R}{a_0} \quad (5)$$

In general, $\omega = \omega(ND)$, which is the vibration frequency in the rotor frame of reference, and St can be expressed as a function of ω , or the nodal diameter, ND . When $M_\theta \neq 0$, $St'(ND) \neq$

$-St'(-ND)$ and the damping curves are not symmetric with respect the ND .

The dimensionless gap or torsion centre, \tilde{z} , includes the effect of the pivot centre of the vibration mode-shape, r , the seal clearance, H , and the geometry of the seal (see Fig. 1) and is defined as

$$\tilde{z} = \frac{\gamma r H}{s L} \quad (6)$$

The parameters \tilde{z} and h' appear always grouped as $\tilde{z}h'$ which is very convenient. The effective value of this nondimensional group $\tilde{z}h'_{eff} = \tilde{z}h'F(\Omega, \eta, r/L)$ accounts for the non-isentropic perturbations and the effect of the differential gapping. The latter is accounted for by using the outlet to inlet gap ratio, $\eta = H_2/H_1$, which in turn includes the contraction of the fluid across each fin, Cd_i , and the kinetic energy carry-over coefficient, χ (the details of the formulation are included in [5], and the reader can find the explicit expression of $\tilde{z}h'_{eff}$ in the nomenclature. Moreover, the parameter $\tilde{z}h'_{eff}$ can be used to conceal other effects such as the slant of seal land [11].

The solution of the problem requires the specification of the temporal and spatial variations along the circumferential direction, z , of the seal volume, $V_{c,2D}(t, z)$, and the gaps $A_{1,2}(t, z)$. The seal is assumed to move as a rigid body around a pivot point, as shown in Fig. 1. For a straight seal the time variations of the control volume and the inlet and outlet areas can be expressed, in non-dimensional form and in the rotor frame of reference, as:

$$\tilde{a}_{1,2} = \frac{(r \pm L/2)}{H_{1,2}} \Delta\theta \sin(\omega'_f t + ND \theta'_f) \quad (7)$$

$$\tilde{v}_c = \frac{r}{s} \Delta\theta \sin(\omega'_f t + ND \theta'_f)$$

where L is the fin spacing, s the inter-fin cavity height, θ'_f and $\omega'_f = \omega + ND(\beta - 1)\Omega_{Rotor}$ are respectively the angle and the angular frequency in the fluid frame of reference, being β the swirl factor within the inter-fin cavity. Finally, the dimensionless work-per-cycle, \tilde{W}_{cyc} , can be written as:

$$\tilde{W}_{cyc} = \frac{W_{cyc}}{\pi p_{c,s} \delta^2 S L / |r| H h'} = \text{sign}(rH_1) \hat{p}_{\text{out-of-phase}} \quad (8)$$

where $\delta = r\Delta\theta$ is the seal torsion displacement in the land mid-point, and $S = 2\pi RL$ the surface of the seal land. The the expression for the dimensionless out-of-phase component of the unsteady pressure is :

$$\hat{p}_{\text{out-of-phase}} = -\tilde{\Omega} \left[\left(\tilde{z}h'_{eff} + \left(1 - \frac{1}{St'^2} \right) \right) \right] / \left[\tilde{1} + \tilde{\Omega}^2 \left(1 - \frac{1}{St'^2} \right)^2 \right] \quad (9)$$

where $\tilde{1}$ is a function of Ω which in practical cases is close to the unity. The physical interpretation of the parameters and their influence on the \tilde{W}_{cyc} are described in detail in [10] and [12].

To account for multiple cavity effects, the same governing equations are solve for each cavity, so that the unsteady pressure

FIGURE 2. Cross section of Kawasaki Heavy Industries (KHI) test rig from [9].

in each inter-fin cavity is obtained. The unsteady interactions among the different cavities are ignored in first approximation. The aerodynamic work-per-cycle of a multi-cavity seal is obtained by integrating and projecting the unsteady pressure along the whole seal surface into the seal displacements. The contributions to the work-per-cycle of each cavity are added to obtain the total work-per-cycle, i.e. $W_{cyc}^{Total} = \sum_i W_i$.

Description of the Test Rig

The simulations and predictions presented in this work correspond to the experimental data obtained in a labyrinth seal flutter test rig performed by Kawasaki Heavy Industries Co. Ltd (KHI) [9] (See Fig. 2). The test specimen, made of structural steel, is attached to the rotor shaft. Figure 3 (a) shows a meridional view of the seal and the upstream and downstream cavities. The rotor is driven by a 3.7 kW electric motor whose speed can be controlled between 0 and 3,960 rpm. The pressure ratio across the test labyrinth can vary between $\pi_T = 1.1$ and 3. The specimen consists of a four-fin seal with a tip diameter of 0.39 m. The depth of each cavity is about 0.01 m, and the height of each fin tip is about 7.6 mm. The radial gap is set to 0.2 mm. The vibration of the seal and the mode were detected by eight strain gauges mounted on the disc. The pressure and the temperature of the rig are measured by sensors located in the high-pressure and low-pressure chambers. The experimental data released by Miura and Sakai [9] include several configurations with different gaps and cavity volumes.

NUMERICAL MODEL

Structural Model

In this work, a disc drum with a four-fin straight-through labyrinth seal located on his outer radius with a stick attachment to the shaft. This boundary condition has been chosen to match

FIGURE 3. Mesh of the fluid computational domain (a) and streamlines of the steady flowfield coloured by the static pressure (b).

the results of the hammer test, since the description of the test rig does not report further details about the connection between the disc and the shaft. The sketch of the rig in Fig. 2 shows that the root of the disc is bolted on his side to the shaft, therefore a clamped condition in this region has been simulated as described in Fig. 4. The comparison between the measured frequencies and the analytical predictions performed in this work are shown on Table 1 showing a good agreement for all the nodal diameters tested. The FEM of the seal consists of a sector of 10° of the whole disc of about 33000 nodes with cyclic symmetry bound-

ND	Hammer Test [Hz]	FEM [Hz]	$\xi_{\text{mech}} \times 10^3$
1	327	304	2.74
2	328	339	1.30
3	1001	988	0.25
4	1948	1918	0.318
5	2971	2930	0.796

TABLE 1. Comparison between the natural frequencies measured by Miura and Sakai [9] and that obtained by the authors using FEM analyses as a function of the nodal diameter. The right column displays the critical damping ratio measured in a hammer test.

FIGURE 4. Sketch of the FEM discretization and boundary conditions of the test specimen.

ary conditions in the lateral patches, as shown in Fig4. To obtain the effective values of the gaps static analysis accounting for the displacements of the seal due to the fluid static pressure and the centrifugal forces was conducted first. It turned out that the pressure difference across the seal was resposingle for most of the axial displacement, as shown in Fig. 5(a).

The numerical tests has been performed by varying the upstream total pressure, P_0 , in order to reproduce the experimental campaign. The outlet pressure is kept constant to the atmospheric pressure, $p_e = 0.1MPa$, the baseline case (- The radial displacement of the fins even for the maximum pressure difference - is very limited, around a 2% – 3% of the nominal gap. The effect of the centrifugal force on the static displacements instead is described in Fig.5 (b). The radial displacement of the seal grows as the square of the tangential velocity. Therefore it is observed that the centrifugal forces induces a reduction of each the gap. The mode-shapes are obtained from a linear FEM as sketched in Fig. 6. The modal analysis reveals that the torsion center is located on the third fin independently of the nodal diameter as reported in [9]. In the meridional plane all the modes are analogous to a

FIGURE 5. Effect of the pressure difference (a) and centrifugal force (b) on the seal displacements coloured with the radial displacements. The red solid line represents the undeformed geometry

FIGURE 6. Snapshot of the seal ND 2 mode-shape coloured with the radial displacements.(a) Mode-shape in the meridional plane compared with the undeformed geometry (solid red line). (b) Outlook of the mode-shape in the whole disc.

rigid body torsion around a pivot point.

Aeroelastic Model

The aerodynamic damping is computed using a frequency-domain linearised Navier-Stokes solver known as $Mu^2s^2T - L$ [13]. The code has been validated extensively and is routinely used, both for aeroelastic and noise analyses. The base flow is obtained from the corresponding non-linear version of the code [14, 15]. The Mu^2s^2T suite of codes solves the fully non-linear or linearised Reynolds-averaged Navier–Stokes equations using the $k - \omega$ turbulence model. The computational domain is sketched in Fig. 3. The size and the position of the inlet and the outlet are chosen to ease the convergence of the simulations. This choice does not cause any impact on the simulations, due to the small mass flow and Mach numbers associated with the jet entering the cavity. The experimental campaign doesn't report the details

FIGURE 7. Comparison between the labyrinth seal flow function measured by Miura and Sakai results [9] (\square) and CFD results obtained by the authors (\circ).

related to the geometry of the outer cavities of the rig, therefore the outer boundaries of the model has been designed based on simplifying assumptions. The downstream cavity length is representative of the test rig, while the upstream plenum axial length is approximately half than that of the rig. The inner radius for both cavities has been chosen close to the attachment of the disc to the shaft in order to retain all the work-per-cycle related to the vibration. The meridional plane (see Fig. 3) is discretized using an hybrid grid of around 30,000 nodes. The model is extruded in the circumferential direction to form a 10 deg sector containing 10 layers. Therefore, the full mesh consists of 300,000 points. Phase-shifted boundary conditions are imposed on the azimuthal boundaries of the computational domain to simulate arbitrary nodal diameters. The mesh is fine enough in the whole domain to ensure that $y^+ \simeq 1$. Two-dimensional non-reflecting boundary conditions are applied both at the inlet and the outlet [16]. The mode-shape displacements are interpolated onto the aerodynamic mesh and then transferred to the inner nodes by using a Laplacian smoother.

MAIN RESULTS

Steady Results

An accurate prediction of the steady-state values is essential for an accurate prediction of the seal stability. Obviously, such prediction cannot be obtained with the simple steady model embedded in the CV model [5]. To reduce the uncertainty a set of steady nonlinear simulations are used to feed the analytical model and derive the discharge coefficients and the carry-over coefficient of each fin, as well as other basic data needed to non-dimensionalize the W_{cyc} , such as the mean pressure of the inter-fin cavity. Figure 7 shows the comparison of the flow function,

FIGURE 8. Schematic view of the labyrinth seal coloured with the static pressure and with the streamlines.

FIGURE 9. Effect of the pressure ratio on the seal closure.

φ :

$$\varphi = \frac{\dot{m}\sqrt{T_0}}{P_0 A_1} \quad (10)$$

between the experimental data and the RANS solver as a function of the total pressure ratio, π_T . The comparison shows that the simulations are in good agreement with the experimental data in the whole range of pressure ratios. It has been previously shown [5] that the analytical model is very sensitive to the outlet to inlet gap ratio, $\eta = H_2/H_1$. To properly compare the experimental data with the analytical model predictions is essential to incorporate the effective gaps in the formulation. The fins and the cavities of the seal have been numbered sequentially following the downstream direction as sketched in Fig. 8. First, the effect of the pressure ratio on the effective gaps is studied. Figure 9 shows the fin displacement as a function of the pressure ratio applied across the seal. As reported in the previous section, all the numerical tests have been performed by changing the upstream pressure, P_0 , keeping constant the outlet pressure, p_e . The nominal gap, H_0 , is set to 0.2 mm.

It can be appreciated that the gap variation is linear since

FIGURE 10. Effect of the disc rim velocity on the seal gaps.

the resulting force varies linearly with the pressure ratio and the FEM is linear as well. The exit gap opens with increasing pressure ratio whereas the inlet gap closes. The ratio between the exit and inlet gap in each inter-fin cavity is about $\eta_j \simeq 0.98$, and therefore this effect is deemed small in terms of seal stability.

The effect of the rotor velocity on the gap variation is described in Fig. 10. The clearance reduction over each fin is quadratic with shaft speed, as the pull load is. The ratio between the exit and inlet gap in each inter-fin cavity is about $\eta_j \simeq 1.03$. This effect is similar but opposite to that of the pressure ratio. However, the impact of the shaft speed in the absolute value of the gap is much bigger than that of the pressure ratio.

Finally, the CFD simulations shows that depending on the pressure ratio, a recirculation bubble over each fin gives rise to a further contraction of the flow. The analytical model takes into account this phenomenon with the discharge coefficient, Cd_i , which is described in [5]-. Due to the small clearance of the seal, the contraction of the flow is very limited. The flutter inception observed in the experiments corresponding to a pressure ratio of $\pi_T = 1.4$ and to a rim speed of $V_\theta = 36.7$ m/s, has been chosen as baseline case. The values of the discharge coefficients corresponding to this operating condition are close to 1 independently of the pressure ratio.-

The accumulated impact of all the effects previously described are summarised in Fig. 11 for the baseline case, $\pi_T = 1.4$. The highest clearance reduction is for the inlet fin. The factor impacting the most on the gap variation is the shaft speed, while the pressure ratio and the contraction of the flow over each fin give rise to a small correction which is relevant for low rotor speeds only.

Unsteady Aerodynamics

The experimental campaign was conducted by varying the pressure ratio and the rotor speed. It was observed that as the

FIGURE 11. Combined effect of the pressure ratio, rotor velocity and the discharge coefficients on the running clearances for a pressure ratio of $\pi_T = 1.4$.

pressure ratio or the rotation speed increased, the seal became susceptible to flutter. When the flutter sets in, only a vibration in the second nodal diameter forward traveling wave is detected.

The stability predicted by the analytical model is sensitive to the kinetic energy carry over coefficient (see [5]). In order to reduce the uncertainties in the comparison with the experiments is essential to derive this parameter from the CFD simulations. The carry-over coefficient, χ , is evaluated in each cavity using the following expression:

$$\chi = \frac{P_{c0,i} - p_i}{P_{0,i-1} - p_i} \quad (11)$$

where $P_{c0,i}$ is the total pressure of the i -th cavity and $P_{0,i-1}$ is the upstream total pressure. Figure. 12 shows the trend of χ as a function of the total pressure ratio.

The kinetic energy carried over is lower in the Cavity 1 and slightly increases downstream cavity (Cavity 3), due to the entry effect of the flow from the plenum upstream to the seal. The nondimensional work-per-cycle of the seal is then evaluated as described in expression 8.

The stability depends on three nondimensional parameters. Firstly, the nondimensional torsion center, $\tilde{e}h'_{eff}$, is represented in Fig. 13 as a function of the total pressure ratio. It is important to recall that the torsion center position of the seal is located around the the Fin 3 (see the sketch in Fig. 8). Therefore, the cavities 1 and 2 are supported on the LPS ($\tilde{e}h'_{eff} > 0$), whereas the Cavity 3 is supported on the HPS ($\tilde{e}h'_{eff} < 0$).

Secondly, the nondimensional discharge time, $\bar{\Omega}$, has been derived from the CFD simulations and is expressed in Fig. 14 as a function of the total pressure ratio for the nodal diameter susceptible to flutter, ND 2. The figure shows that the nondimensional discharge time increases with the pressure ratio and

FIGURE 12. Kinetic energy carry-over coefficient as a function of the pressure ratio.

FIGURE 14. Nondimensional discharge time of the ND 2 derived from the CFD simulations, $\bar{\Omega}$, as function of the total pressure ratio, π_T for the nominal velocity, $V_\theta = 36.7$ m/s.

FIGURE 13. Nondimensional stability parameter $\bar{e}h'$ as a function of the total pressure ratio.

the curves are similar for each cavity of the seal. It is useful to recall that in practical cases, the values of the nondimensional discharge time of the seal used to be $\bar{\Omega} \gg 1$ but due to the low frequency associated to the ND 2 and to the relatively low pressure ratio -across each cavity (which means $h' \gg 1$), the values of $\bar{\Omega}$ are close to 1 for all the operating conditions. Third, the frequency ratio, St , is evaluated by the expression 4 and considering the frequency extracted by the FEM simulations and reported for the baseline case in Tab. 1. For the ND 2 and for the nominal velocity, $V_\theta = 36.7$ m/s, the frequency ratio, St , is a function of the swirl factor, β , only. In the range of the pressure ratio tested the variation of the swirl factor is very limited ($\beta \simeq 0.6 - 0.7$) therefore the frequency ratio is around $St = 0.56$.

FIGURE 15. Aerodynamic critical damping ratio of the baseline case, ($\pi_T = 1.4$, $V_\theta = 36.7$ m/s) as a function of the nodal diameter. Comparison between the CV model prediction and the three-dimensional CFD results. A positive nodal diameter is associated to a forward travelling wave

Finally, the critical aerodynamic damping defined as

$$\xi = \frac{\text{Im}(W_{cyc})}{2\pi\omega^2 m \delta^2} \quad (12)$$

where m is the modal mass, ω the natural frequency and δ the maximum displacement of the seal has been computed compared with. The critical damping ratio of the seal has been computed using the linearised Navier-Stokes solver and the analytical model for the baseline case and compared in Fig. 15.

Figure 15 highlights that only the ND=2 is unstable, which is consistent with the experimental campaign where only the vibra-

FIGURE 16. Total damping of the ND 2 for the baseline case, as a function of the total pressure, π_T . Comparison between the CFD simulations and the predictions of the analytical model. Sum of the aerodynamic damping and the mechanical damping derived from the hammer test.

tion associated with the second forward ND was measured. Due to the relatively slow rotational speed the aerodynamic damping of the forward and backward modes are similar. However, the CV model shows that the forward mode is more unstable than the backward mode for the second ND. The instability predictions are accurate for all the tested nodal diameters. It is well known that the upstream and downstream cavities can exhibit a large level of unsteadiness that can eventually influence the dynamics of the seal. However, in the range of operating condition tested the unsteady pressure of the outer cavities remains very low and the contribution on the stability of the disc is limited.

In the experiments the operating conditions of the baseline case are representative of the flutter boundary, instead the numerical results show that the second ND 2 is unstable for a wide range of the pressure ratios, as reported in Fig. . The hammer test of the seal was used to derive the mechanical damping which is reported in Table 1. This mechanical damping can be added to the aerodynamic damping of the analytical model and of the CFD in order to compare the predictions with the experiments. Considering both dampings the flutter boundary of the baseline case increases to a higher pressure ratio. Fig. 16 shows the numerical damping of the ND 2 as a function of the total pressure ratio. The addition of the mechanical damping shifts the flutter inception to a higher pressure ratio, $\pi_T = 1.7$.

In fig. 15 is clear that the ND 2 is the only mode susceptible of flutter. In order to understand which is the origin of the instability, each cavity has been studied separately. In Fig. 17 the stability of the ND 2 has been analyzed as a function of the pressure ratio for the nominal velocity, $V_\theta = 36.7$ m/s. The maps include the critical frequency ratio, St_{cr} , derived from the analytical model imposing that $\tilde{W}_{cyc}(St_c) = 0$, leading to the following

expression:

$$St_{cr} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + \tilde{e}_{eff} h'}} + (1 - \beta) M_\theta \quad (13)$$

which is a generalization of the criterion derived in [12] including the impact of the dissimilar gaps. As previously described, the impact of the pressure on the gaps is limited, therefore the gap ratio is around $\eta = 0.95$ independently of the cavity and of the pressure ratio. Therefore the stability pattern of this seal is close to that described in [10], characterized by an unstable region for values of $St < 1$ when the support is located on the LPS and also for $St > 1$ when the support is on the HPS. It is important to clarify that in Fig. 17 we should have marked a critical curve for each pressure ratio. But, as previously described, in the range of the pressure ratio tested the swirl number, β , and the gap ratio, η , are both constant therefore all the critical curves overlap the same trend, hence only one critical curve has been pictured. The upstream cavity (Fig. 17,a) and the central cavity (Fig. 17,b) are supported on the LPS and the ND 2 is inside of the unstable region. Increasing the pressure ratio, the points on the maps move towards lower values of $\tilde{e} h'$, increasing the instability. This trend is due to the function h' which decreases monotonically when the pressure ratio increases. The downstream cavity (Fig. 17,c) instead which is supported on the HPS, is stable independently of the pressure ratio. The position of the ND 2 on the stability map changes as described previously or the others cavities, increasing the stability when the pressure ratio increases.

CONCLUSIONS

This paper compares the predictions of an analytical model for seal flutter described in [5] with the experimental data obtained for a rotating multi-cavity labyrinth seal obtained in a dedicated rig [9] for the first time. The comparison shows that the analytical predictions agree well with the experimental data in the whole range of the tested operating conditions. It is concluded that the CV model can be used to obtain a quick, and accurate predictions of seal flutter provided that the steady flow-field and running clearance of the seal are well predicted. The method can be easily integrated in an industrial production loop.

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FIGURE 17. ND 2 stability map as a function of the pressure ratio of each cavity of the seal. The seal is rotating at a tip velocity of $V_\theta = 36.7$ m/s. The upstream cavity (a) and the central cavity (b) are supported on the LPS, instead the downstream cavity (c) is supported on the HPS.

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